

ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY OF DRIED LEAVES OF *Aginanthus brunneus* ON ALLOXAN-INDUCED DIABETIC RATS

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ABSTRACT

The present study was aimed at evaluating the antidiabetic potential of *Aginanthus brunneus* (a specie of Africa mistletoe) leaves on alloxan induced experimental diabetes in wister Albino rats. Oral administration of ethanolic extracts of the leaves (200mg/kg body weight/rat/day) for 30 days significantly reduced the levels of blood glucose and glycosylated hemoglobin in diabetic rats. Determination of plasma insulin levels revealed the insulin stimulating action of the leaf extracts. Furthermore, the changes observed in the activities of carbohydrate and glycogen metabolizing enzymes were reverted back to normal after 30 days of treatment with the extracts. The efficacy of the leaf extracts was comparable with Gliben clamide (a sulphony urea), a well known hypoglyceamic drug.

KEYWORDS: *Aginanthus brunneus*, Eucalyptus, Ethanolic extract, diabetes carbohydrate metabolism, Glibenclamide.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is considered as one of the leading causes of death in the world about 160 million people are suffering from diabetes mellitus worldwide. Diabetes is a complex multisystemic disorder characterized by a relative or absolute insufficiency of insulin secretion insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) or concomitant resistance of metabolic action of insulin on target tissues non insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) (Garber. A 1998). There is need for search for drugs with low cost, more potentials, and without adverse side effects which is being searched for throughout the world.

Many traditional plants have been found successful for ant diabetic activity. It is necessary to provide scientific proof as to whether it is justified to use a plant or its active principles for treatment (Singh et al 2000). This parasitic plant *Aginanthus brunneus* parasitizing on Eucalyptus is native to Nigeria and belongs to the Loranthaceae family of Africa mistletoe.

FIGURE 1: *Aginanthus brunneus* parasitizing on *Eucalyptus*

Being a parasite, it is unable to acquire all the nutrient it needs by its own independent processes and hence takes what it needs from it's living host through special sucker-like outgrowth which penetrate the tissues of the host plant. No systematic work on it's antidiabetogenic activity has been reported in literature. Hence the present study was aimed to evaluate the pharmacologic effect of ethanolic extract of *Aginanthus brunneus* on carbohydrate and

glycogen metabolism in both normal and alloxan induced diabetic rats. The effects of *Aginanthus brunneus* were compared to glibenclamide that is often used as a standard drug.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CHEMICAL

Alloxan was purchased from sigma chemical co U.S.A All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

PLANT MATERIAL

Fresh mature *Globimetulla brownii* (Loranthaceae) leaves were collected from Eucalyptus tree in botanical garden of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria. The plant was identified and authenticated by Mr. U.S. Galla of biological Sciences Department with a voucher number 1968

Preparation of *Aginanthus brunneus* Extracts

Dried leaves were powdered in an electrical grinder and stored at 5°C until further use. 100g of the powder was extracted with petroleum ether (60-80°C) to remove lipids it was then filtered and the filtrate discarded the residue was extracted with 95% ethanol by Soxhlet extraction. The ethanol was evaporated in a rotary evaporator at 40-50°C under reduced pressure. The yield of the extract was 8.5g/100g.

Animals

Adults male albino rat of Wistar strain weighing approximately 150 – 180g were procured from NITOR (Nigerian Institute for Trypanosomiasis and Oncocerciasis Research) Kaduna and were acclimatized to Animal house conditions in the department of Applied Science, Kaduna Polytechnic, Kaduna, Nigeria and fed with standard rat feeds supplied by Pfizer feeds.

Toxicity studies

To study any possible toxic effects and/or changes in behavioral pattern, rats were treated with graded doses of *Aginanthus brunneus* extract (100 – 500 mg 1kg body weight/rat/day) and kept under close observation for 8 hr daily for 30 days.

Induction of Experimental diabetes

The animals were fasted overnight and diabetes was induced by a single intraperitoneal injection of a freshly prepared Alloxan solution (50mg/1kg body weight) in 0.1m citrate buffer (pH 4.5) (Sekar et al (1990). The animals were allowed to drink 5% glucose solution overnight to overcome the drug induced hypoglycemia. Control rats were infected with citrate buffer alone. After a week time for the development of diabetes, the rats with moderate diabetes having glycosuria and hypoglycemia (blood glucose range above 250mg/dl) were considered diabetic and used for drug treatment. The leaf treatment was administered orally at a concentration of 200 mg/1kg body weight/rat/day for 30 day.

Experimental design

The animals were divided into two sets, one for the evaluation of a glucose tolerance test and a second one for the analysis of biochemical parameters. Each set was further divided into four groups, each comprising a minimum of six animals in each group shown below: Group i: Normal control rats

Group ii: Diabetic control rats

Group iii: Diabetic rats administered *Aginanthus brunneus* leaf extracts (200mg 1kg body weight) Day/ rat) in aqueous solution orally for 30days (*Pari et al 2000*)

Group iv: Diabetic rats administered with glibenclamide (600 mg 1kg body weight/rat/day)

In aqueous solution orally for 30days (*Pau et al 2000*).

The body weight gain and fasting blood glucose levels of all the rats were recorded at regular intervals during the experimental period

Glucose Tolerance Test

After 30 days of treatment, a fasting blood sample was collected from all the groups in heparinized tubes blood samples were also collected at the time intervals of 30, 60, 90 and 120 min after administration of the glucose at a concentration of 2g/kg of body weight (Joy *et al* 1999)

Biochemical Assays

After 30 days of treatment, a fasting blood sample was collected from all the groups, and were sacrificed by cervical decapitation, fasting blood glucose was estimated by 0-toluidine method of (Sasaki *et al* 1972). The levels of hemoglobin and glycosylated hemoglobin were estimated according to the method of Drabkin *et al* (1972) Nayak *et al* (1981) respectively the hexokinase activity was assayed by the method of Brandstrup *et al* (1967).

The activities of glucose – 6- phosphatase and fructose 1, 6 – bis phosphatase were assayed according to the method of Koide and Oda (1999) and Gancedo and Gancedo (1971) respectively, Lactate dehydrogenase by Kind (1999), Glycogen synthesis (Leloir *et al* (1982) and phosphorylase by Cornblath (1973).

RESULTS

Fig 1 changes in Body weight of control and Experimental Groups of Rats

Fig 1 shows the change in weight gain of control and experimental groups of rats. There was significant decrease in the body weight of diabetic rats compared with control rats. Upon treatment with *Globimetulla brownii* and glibenclamide the body weight gain was improved but the effect was more pronounced in *Aginanthus brunneus* treated rats than glibenclamide.

Fig 2 Glucose Tolerance Test Graph of Control and Experimental Groups of Rats.

The levels of blood glucose in control and experimental groups of rats after oral administration of glucose is shown in figure 2 the blood glucose value in the control rats rose to a peak value 60min after glucose load and decreased to near normal level at 120min. in diabetic control rats, the peak increase in blood glucose concentration was observed after 60min and remained high over the next 60min. *Aginanthus brunneus* and glibenclamide treated diabetic rats showed significant decrease in blood glucose concentration at 60 and 120min compared with diabetic groups of rats.

Table 1 changes in the level of blood glucose, plasma insulin, Hemoglobin, Glycosylated Hemoglobin and Urine Sugar in Control and Experimental Groups of Rats

Group	Blood Glucose mg/dl	Plasma insulin μ U/ml	Hemoglobin g/dl	Glycosylated Hemoglobin (% Hb A1c)	Urine sugar
Control	74.324 \pm 4.61	15.44 \pm 1.07	12.42 \pm 0.91	5.23 \pm 0.46	Nil
Diabetic control	245.08 \pm 20.14	5.27 \pm 0.76	8.46 \pm 0.67	11.36 \pm 0.91	+++
Diabetic + <i>Aginanthus brunneus</i>	91.40 \pm 7.09	14.26 \pm 0.81	12.93 \pm 0.82	5.55 \pm 0.40	Nil
Diabetic + Glibenclamide	104.40 \pm 6.33	14.86 \pm 0.62	12.46 \pm 0.77	6.95 \pm 0.42	+

Table 1 shows the level of blood glucose, plasma insulin, total hemoglobin, glycosylated hemoglobin and urine sugar in normal and experiment rats.

There was a significant elevation in blood glucose, urine sugar and glycosylated hemoglobin, while the level of plasma insulin and total hemoglobin decreased during diabetes when compared to control group. Administration of *Aginanthus brunneus* brought back to near normal values as that of the standard drug glibenclamide treatment.

Table 2: changes in the activities of hepatic hexokinase, lactate dehydrogenase, Glucose 6 phosphatase and fructose 1,6 Bisphosphatase of control and Experimental Groups of Rats

Group	Hexokinase hr/mg protein	Lactate dehydrogenase (pyruvate formed/hr/mg)	Glucose-6-phosphatase liberated/hr/mg protein	Fructose 1, 6 bisphosphatase hr/mg protein
Control	262.6 \pm 15.5	236.33 \pm 14.88	1032 \pm 74.30	412 \pm 19.88
Diabetic control	129.3 \pm 27.09	346.45 \pm 27.09	1967 \pm 184.99	739 \pm 55.42
Diabetic + <i>Aginanthus brunneus</i>	275.1 \pm 16.78	243.92 \pm 18.90	1051 \pm 77.50	500 \pm 4.45
Diabetic + Glibenclamide	248.2 \pm 16.50	278.33 \pm 15.90	1215 \pm 104.36	541 \pm 22.5

Table 2 shows a significant decrease in the activity of hepatic hexokinase, a significant increase in the activities of lactate dehydrogenase, glucose-6-phosphatase and fructose 1, 6 bis phosphatase, in Alloxan induced diabetic rats when compared to control rats.

Treatment with *Aginanthus brunneus* extracts (group iii) and glibenclamide (Group iv) significantly controlled the alterations and restored the altered levels to near normalcy. *Aginanthus brunneus* treatment exerted more effect than glibenclamide in diabetic rats.

DISCUSSION

Glibenclamide is often used as a standard antidiabetic drug in Alloxan induced moderate diabetes to compare the efficacy of a variety of hypoglycemic compounds. (Paredes et al 2000). The present study was conducted to assess the hypoglycemic activity of *Aginanthus brunneus* leaves on alloxan induced diabetic rats the ability of *Aginanthus brunneus* leaf extract in significantly increasing the body weight and effectively controlling the increase in blood glucose levels in diabetic group of rats may be attributed to its antihyperglycemic effects. Further, the antihyperglycemic activity of *Aginanthus brunneus* was associated with an increase in plasma insulin level suggesting an insulinogenic activity of the leaf extract. The observed increase in the level of plasma indicates that *Aginanthus brunneus* leaf extracts stimulates insulin secretion from the remnant β cells or from regenerated β cells

the observed increase in the levels of glycosylated hemoglobin in diabetic control group of rats is due to the presence of excessive amounts of blood glucose.

The hepatic gluconeogenic enzymes, glucose 6 phosphatase and fructose 1, 6 bisphosphatase were increased significantly in diabetic rats. The increased activities of these two gluconeogenic enzymes may be due to the activation or increased synthesis of the enzymes contributing to the increased glucose production during diabetes by the liver (Baque *et al* 1998). In the present study, the experimental diabetic rats treated with *Aginanthus brunneus* leaf extract and glibenclamide treated groups restored the level of hepatic glycogen by means of decreasing the activity of glycogen phosphorylase and increasing the activity of glycogensynthase.

In conclusion, the present work/study show that the ethanolic extract of *Aginanthus brunneus* leaves has potential hypoglycemic action in alloxan induced diabetic rats and the effect was found to be more effective than glibenclamide.

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